

Limitation of gene flow by distance in the common yellow jasmine (*Chrysojasminum fruticans*, Oleaceae): implications for the study of its mating strategies

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ABSTRACT

The common yellow jasmine (*Chrysojasminum fruticans*; Oleaceae) is a distylous shrub occurring in the wild in southwestern Europe and the Mediterranean Basin. Little is known about the genetics of its populations and such information would be necessary to investigate its spread and mating strategies. Here, the organization of its genetic diversity was investigated among and between 13 populations from southern France, including a 35-years old experimental plot ('CEFE', CNRS Montpellier). Markers (microsatellites and indels) were developed to screen polymorphisms in nuclear, chloroplast, and mitochondrial genomes. Low linkage disequilibrium was observed between chloroplast and mitochondrial haplotypes likely resulting from paternal leaks in their inheritance as reported in other species of tribe Jasmineae. Yet, analyses of 36 progenies issued from parents with distinct chloroplast and/or mitochondrial DNA haplotypes only revealed a maternal contribution. Natural populations of *C. fruticans* are moderately to highly differentiated at the regional scale with a strong isolation-by-distance pattern detected on nuclear data, indicating limited gene flow. An isolated site ('Moullis'), located on the marginal distribution area, was remarkably genetically depauperate and highly differentiated from other populations. Further studies on the variation of mating strategies in *C. fruticans* should consider populations with contrasting patterns of genetic diversity. The artificial 'CEFE' population also offers opportunities for experiments in a closed system.

ADDITIONAL KEYWORDS: Chloroplast genome – Heterostyly – IBD – Jasmineae – Microsatellite – Mitochondrial genome – Organelle paternal leakage – Population genetics – Self-incompatibility.

INTRODUCTION

Many ecological and evolutionary processes directly depend on how genetic diversity is structured within and among natural populations. For instance, levels of genetic variation and patterns of gene flow among populations determine both the opportunity for selection and the geographical scale at which selection can act (Slatkin, 1987; Sork, 2016). In plants, this mainly depends on dispersal strategies of pollen and seeds, but also on cross-compatibilities between individuals (Barrett, 2002; Charlesworth, 2006). Beyond the acknowledged usefulness of population genetics descriptors for applied purposes, such as conservation biology, describing the distribution of genetic diversity in a species also constitutes the first step of many basic research studies, in particular those that investigate the ecology and evolution of reproductive systems.

The common yellow jasmine [*Chrysojasminum fruticans* (L.) Banfi; Oleaceae] is a distylous shrub, which is the only native European species of Jasmineae, the sister lineage of the olive tribe or Oleaceae (Wallander and Albert, 2000; Dupin *et al.*, 2020). In various members of Oleaceae, a homomorphic self-incompatibility (SI) system with only two groups (di-allelic SI: DSI) has been discovered. This unusual DSI, compared to highly diversified SI (see for instance Bush *et al.*, 2010), asks the question of its maintenance as well as its potential role in the evolution of separate sexes in Oleaceae (Vassiliadis *et al.*, 2000; Saumitou-Laprade *et al.*, 2010; Vernet *et al.*, 2016; Billiard *et al.*, 2015). In addition, a

breakdown of the same DSI system has been documented in some individuals of one Oleaceae species (de Cauwer *et al.*, 2021). No information of the genetic structure is currently available in the common yellow jasmine, and more generally in any species of Jasmineae. Such data has both practical and theoretical importance: (i) studying levels of variation will help in defining molecular markers and identifying populations of potential interest; (ii) measurements of heterozygosity should provide some indirect insight on the mating system and on possible breakdown of the DSI; and (iii) patterns of gene flow through both seed and pollen may help us to infer geographical scale at which evolutionary processes take place.

Our study species (*C. fruticans*) occurs in the wild in southwestern Europe and the Mediterranean Basin (Dommée, Thompson & Cristini, 1992; Olesen *et al.*, 2003; Banfi, 2014). It is generally found on dry and sunny soils of hillsides, often rocky with a slight preference for limestone, leading to a heterogeneous and fragmented habitat. The species is a small rhizomatous semi-evergreen shrub with slightly fragrant yellow flowers, which appear from April to June, and small black berries (0.5 cm in diameter) in the autumn. Individuals of *C. fruticans* either have “pin” flowers (long style and low anthers = longistylous) or “thrum” flowers (short style and high anthers = brevistylous), and reciprocal crosses mostly occur between the two morphs (Dommée, Thompson & Cristini, 1992; Gutiérrez, Gutiérrez & Medrano, 1998). Pollination and seed dispersal are respectively mediated by numerous insects of different orders (Thompson, 2001) and by birds (Puech, 1986). A generalist pollination system that may impede specialization of the plant to particular pollinators has been notably described by Thompson (2001). On the other hand, no study has specifically documented fruit dispersal of *C. fruticans*, but its frequent occurrence in abandoned cultivated areas and firebreaks suggests an efficient spread at the local scale (e.g. Debussche, Escarré & Lepart, 1982). Although pollinated by an insect community and its fruits spread by birds, the dispersal of the common yellow jasmine should be limited by geographic distance due to its occurrence in a fragmented habitat. A strong structure of its genetic diversity among populations is therefore expected, but gene flow measured on the organellar genomes or on the nuclear genome should not be impacted in the same way due to their different transmission modes (Petit *et al.*, 2005).

In this study, we thus aim at describing the population genetics of *Chrysojasminum fruticans* in southern France, in particular the isolation by distance (IBD) and the genetic differentiation between populations. Patterns of genetic diversity on different genomic compartments were investigated and compared to assess the relative contribution of pollen and seeds in the global gene flow. First, genotyping methods (microsatellites and indels) were developed to screen polymorphisms in nuclear, chloroplast, and mitochondrial genomes, which should show contrasting mutation rates (Wolfe *et al.*, 1987) and could therefore also give complementary information about the impact of demographic processes operating at different historical scales on the species genetic variability and structure. The inheritance of both cytoplasmic organelles was beforehand tested in a few progenies in order to ensure that their polymorphisms can be used to study seed dispersal. A marked genetic differentiation between populations was detected, especially on nuclear data for which a strong IBD was observed confirming a limitation of gene flow, especially for the pollen. The implications of our results for investigating mating strategies in *C. fruticans* were finally briefly discussed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

PLANT SAMPLING AND DNA EXTRACTION

Leaves of a total of 196 individuals ('ramets') from 13 French populations and one Spanish population were collected and preserved in silica gel (Table 1). To avoid sampling clones, we collected ramets that were at least 3 m apart. Floral morph and GPS coordinates of individuals (or populations) were also recorded (Table 1; Supporting Information, Table S1). Although style length varies in both morphs (Thompson & Dommée, 2000), the distinction between brevistylous (B) and longistylous (L) individuals has never been ambiguous on open flowers. In addition, 15 herbarium specimens from the Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle de Paris (MNHN-P) were sampled (Supporting Information, Table S2), representing *Chrysojasminum fruticans* populations throughout its range (from Morocco-Portugal in the

West to Iran-Turkmenistan in the East). Nine of those specimens were collected more than a century ago. Those specimens were used as outgroups to our study and also allowed us to test the utility of our markers over the whole distribution area of *C. fruticans*. All populations sampled in this study are assumed to have a natural origin, with the exception of the one from the “plateforme des terrains d’expérience du LabEx CeMEB” (‘CEFE’, Centre d’Étude Fonctionnelle et Evolutive de Montpellier), known to have an artificial origin since it was planted ca. 35 years ago by John D. Thompson and Bertrand Dommée, with individuals from different localities near Montpellier.

The DNA of each sample was extracted with the BioSprint DNA Plant Kit (QIAGEN). About 20 mg of material was placed in a 2-mL tube with three tungsten beads and frozen at -80°C for one hour before being crushed using TissueLyser II (QIAGEN). Then, after one hour of incubation at 65°C in 500 µL of 2X CTAB buffer, DNA extraction was performed following the supplier’s protocol. Finally, the DNA was resuspended in 130 µL of TE buffer and stored at 4°C.

Table 1. List of sampled populations, with their location and geographic coordinates. All populations except one (‘La Aliseda’, Spain) are located in France. Nr and Ng refer to the number of collected ‘ramets’ and of recorded genotypes (after excluding clones), respectively. For each French locality, the number of brevistylous (B) and longistylous (L) genotypes is given in bracket (for more details see Supporting Information, Table S1). Lat. = Latitude; Long. = Longitude.

Locality	Department (or province)	Lat., Long.	Nr	Ng (B/L)
La Aliseda	Jaén	38.335, -3.569	10	7
Amélie-les-Bains	Pyrénées Orientales	42.478, 2.666	9	5 (3/2)
Bages	Aude	43.132, 2.985	12	12 (8/4)
Bidon	Ardèche	44.370, 4.532	10	10 (5/5)
CEFE (Montpellier)	Hérault	43.638, 3.862	15	15 (6/9)
Celleneuve	Hérault	43.611, 3.821	21	21 (10/11)
Eguilles	Bouches du Rhône	43.601, 5.2669	10	10 (5/5)
Moulis	Ariège	42.979, 1.084	37	37 (18/19)
Moussoulens	Aude	43.286, 2.249	15	15 (8/7)
Prades-le-Lez	Hérault	43.693, 3.861	11	10 (5/5)
Puycelsi	Tarn	44.015, 1.676	14	14 (8/6)
Sainte-Baume	Bouches du Rhône	43.327, 5.657	10	10 (4/6)
St-Maurice-Navacelles	Hérault	43.891, 3.510	17	17 (8/9)
La Turbie	Alpes Maritimes	43.747, 7.411	5	3 (1/2)

GENOPYING PROCEDURE

To genetically characterize all the sampled *C. fruticans* individuals, we developed 29 nuclear DNA loci (including 23 microsatellites and six indels) and 15 cytoplasmic loci [five mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) loci (four indels and one microsatellite) and ten chloroplast DNA (cpDNA) loci (two indels and eight microsatellites)] (Supporting Information, Tables S3 to S5). We used shotgun genome sequencing data (*i.e.* HiSeq data on individual ‘Celleneuve L11’) to random search and assemble microsatellite or indel regions as described in Salmona *et al.* (2020). All assembled nuclear sequences are deposited in GenBank. In contrast, the cytoplasmic DNA loci were developed from length polymorphisms revealed on plastomes and mitogenomes of individuals collected in France (GenBank no MH559274, and OQ124187 to OQ124196). The primers used to amplify the 44 loci are given in the Supporting Information (Tables S3 to S5). All primers were defined to have the same annealing temperature (T_m).

Some markers were amplified alone (simplex), while others were amplified in multiplex (either two markers for nuclear loci, or three or four for cytoplasmic loci). The PCR conditions are those reported by Besnard *et al.* (2011). These amplifications were performed in a total volume of 25 µL following the method of Schuelke (2000), which allows the integration of fluorescence on fragments amplified with a dye-labeled M13 primer. Three different fluorochromes were used depending on the markers: 6-FAM, ATTO565 and HEX. The PCR multiplexes and the fluorochrome used for each locus

are given in the Supporting Information (Tables S3 to S5). The same PCR program was used for all markers: denaturation of the DNA at 95°C for 2 min followed by 25 cycles with a 30 sec denaturation at 95°C, followed by an annealing at 55°C and then a 90 sec elongation at 72°C. Ten additional cycles with a lowered annealing temperature of 51.5°C allowing integration of the dye-labeled M13 primer into amplified fragments were added and were followed by a final elongation of 20 min at 72°C.

After PCR amplification, the markers were multiplexed (several markers of different sizes were mixed together) in formamide with ROX-500 (Applied Biosystems) used as internal size standard. The amplified fragments at each locus were separated by chromatography on an ABI 3730 capillary sequencer (Applied Biosystems) by GenoScreen (Lille). The chromatograms were then read on GENEIOUS v.9.1.2 (Kearse *et al.*, 2012). To limit reading errors, all loci were read twice independently by AP and GB.

DEFINING CYTOPLASMIC HAPLOTYPES AND NETWORK RECONSTRUCTION

For chloroplastic and mitochondrial genomes, polymorphisms were revealed at multiple loci (see above). Plastid and mitochondrial DNA profiles (chlorotypes and mitotypes) were defined by the combination of alleles from these loci. Relationships between chlorotypes on one hand, and between mitotypes on the other hand, were established by constructing a reduced-median haplotype network with NETWORK v.10.2 (Bandelt, Forster & Röhl, 1999). All polymorphisms observed were coded as in Gryta *et al.* (2017) [*i.e.* number of repeats for microsatellites, or binary (0/1) for indels].

ON THE INHERITANCE OF ORGANELLES IN *C. FRUTICANS*

As potential for paternal leakage of chloroplasts and mitochondria has been previously reported in several *Jasminum* species (Sodmergen *et al.*, 1998; Zhang, Liu & Sodmergen, 2003), it was necessary to check the inheritance of organelles in *C. fruticans*. As a first source of evidence, we measured the linkage disequilibrium (LD) between chlorotypes and mitotypes. In the case of a strict maternal inheritance, we expect a strong LD (as already shown in beet, *Silene*, and olive; Desplanque *et al.*, 2000; Olson & McCauley, 2000; Besnard *et al.*, 2002). In contrast, the presence of a few paternal leakages may reduce LD between haplotypes of the two organelle genomes. The LD was estimated with Lewontin's normalized D' (Lewontin, 1964, 1988), and its significance was tested with Fisher's exact tests using ARLEQUIN (Excoffier & Lischer, 2010). The D' index was calculated (i) separately on each sampled population where polymorphism was observed on both organellar genomes, and (ii) on all French individuals considered as a single population. Then, we also verified the inheritance of organelles in a few progenies (*i.e.* seeds resulting from open pollination) for which parents display different cpDNA and/or mtDNA haplotypes. In the 'CEFE' and 'Moulis' populations, we previously identified 36 progenies issued from such crosses (*i.e.* 33 with a different chlorotype, and 32 with a different mitotype; Supporting Information, Table S6). Genotyping of the chloroplastic and mitochondrial haplotypes in these progenies allowed us to determine from which parent cytoplasmic organelles were inherited.

POPULATION GENETICS ANALYSES

To avoid bias in population genetics analyses due to repetitions of the same individual, clones (genets) needed to be excluded. In a population, plants sampled a few meters apart may correspond to ramets from the same stump, and the probability of finding the same genotype at 29 multi-allelic nuclear loci is theoretically very low (e.g. Baali-Cherif & Besnard, 2005). Thus, when several close individuals shared the same genotype or a very similar genotype (*i.e.* differing by a mutation step on a long allele), we considered them as a clone. In this case, only one ramet was kept for analyses. In order to represent the genetic proximity between all analyzed individuals, Bruvo *et al.* (2004) genetic distances were first calculated on the nuclear microsatellite data between each pair of genotypes with the R package *Poppr* (Kamvar, Tabima & Grünwald, 2014) and a dendrogram was reconstructed according to the unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA). For further analyses, we only considered populations with at least seven genotypes.

Populations' genetic diversity

Genetic diversity patterns were described for each population. First, observed (H_O) and expected (H_E) heterozygosities under the Hardy-Weinberg ideal population model (*i.e.* population of infinite size, panmictic reproduction, non-overlapping generations), and the Weir & Cockerham Fixation Index (F_{IS} , Weir & Cockerham, 1984) were calculated using the GENETIX software (Belkhir *et al.*, 2004) for each nuclear locus. Allelic richness (A_R) was calculated with the R package HIERFSTAT (Goudet, 2005) to compare the number of alleles between populations. The presence of null alleles was tested for each population with a 95%-confidence interval using MICRO-CHECKER v.2.2.3 (van Oosterhout *et al.*, 2004). As all loci were successfully amplified, the null allele frequency was estimated according to Brookfield (1996). For cytoplasmic data (cpDNA and mtDNA), haplotypic diversity was calculated from the formula $D = 1 - \sum p_i^2$ with p_i the frequency of haplotype i and was multiplied by $n / (n - 1)$ to account for differences in sample sizes, as described in Gryta *et al.* (2017). This parameter was estimated independently for chloroplast and mitochondrial data (D_{cp} and D_{mt}), and for their combination (D_{cp+mt}).

Genetic structure of populations

To measure genetic differentiation between populations, the fixation index F_{ST} of Weir & Cockerham (1984) was calculated between each pair of populations using GENETIX. These calculations were performed separately for nuclear data (bi-paternally transmitted, and thus dispersed by pollen and seed) and cytoplasmic data (assumed to be maternally transmitted, and dispersed by seed). However, for cytoplasmic data, the main mode of transmission of plastids and mitochondria remains uncertain in Jasmineae (Sodmergen *et al.*, 1998; Zhang, Liu & Sodmergen, 2003). Occasional paternal transmission of one or both cytoplasmic genomes could impact on differentiation patterns between populations. Because of this uncertainty, we estimated the F_{ST} of the cytoplasmic data using four different approaches: (i) only on haplotypes of the chloroplast genome, (ii) only on haplotypes of the mitochondrial genome, (iii) considering the chloroplast and mitochondrial genomes as two independent cytoplasmic loci, and (iv) combining cpDNA and mtDNA information to define cytoplasmic haplotypes. Patterns of isolation by distance (IBD) were then compared between each approach. The geographical distribution of cpDNA and mtDNA haplotypes across populations was also mapped using QGIS v.3.0.3 (QGIS Development Team, 2018).

In order to determine the number of genetic clusters actually present in our sample and to assess the isolation between populations, a Bayesian approach was then used to assign individuals to genetic clusters on the basis of their genotypes. STRUCTURE v.2.3.4 (Pritchard, Stephens & Donnelly, 2000) was used on the nuclear data set. For this analysis, the Spanish population ('La Aliseda') was excluded due to its great distance from all the other studied populations and the absence of intermediate populations between them. The artificial 'CEFE' population was also excluded in order not to bias the analyses (*e.g.* due to admixture between individuals). This analysis was carried out under the admixture model (mixing of gametes possible at reproduction) for a duration of 200,000 generations after a burn-in period of 50,000 generations. The analysis was performed for a number of clusters (K) ranging from 1 to 14 with ten iterations for each value of K . The most likely number of clusters was determined using the *ad hoc* measure of ΔK performed with STRUCTURE HARVESTER (Earl & vonHoldt, 2012). In order to determine the putative origin of the artificial CEFE population, we then assigned each individual from this location to the ten natural French populations (with at least ten genets) using GENECLASS2 (Piry *et al.*, 2004). The standard criterion described by Rannala & Mountain (1997) was used to compute the probabilities with Bayesian statistics. The population assignment simulation algorithm described by Paetkau *et al.* (2004) was used in order to simulate 10,000 genotypes for each population. An arbitrary threshold probability value of 0.05 or greater was then applied to identify the possible origin of CEFE genotypes among natural populations.

Limitation of gene flow by distance and relative contribution of pollen and seeds

As IBD was expected, Mantel (1967) tests between geographical distances and F_{ST} values between pairs of populations were performed in southern France on the ten natural populations with at least ten genotypes. These tests were done with 999 permutations using the R package *ade4* (Chessel, Dufour &

Thioulouse, 2004) for each genomic compartment in order to compare patterns according to the origin of the data (nuclear vs. cytoplasmic). In addition, the relative contribution of pollen and seeds in the global gene flow (R) was investigated following the method of Ennos (1994). This approach allows an indirect estimation of pollen and seed flows from genetic differentiation estimates (F_{ST}) on both biparentally inherited nuclear markers (F_{STn}) and maternally inherited cytoplasmic markers (F_{STc}). The R estimation is based on a model of island migration (Wright, 1965), and can be used under several assumptions: (i) a very low mutation rate compared to migration rate, (ii) a constant and equal size of populations, and (iii) a constant and equal migration rate between populations, the last two points representing a drift/migration equilibrium. This equilibrium turns out to be rapidly reached in nature (Slatkin, 1993). However, when the species has a long generation time and/or if perturbations are quite recent, it might be necessary to check these assumptions. In addition, the precision of estimates of genetic differentiation used to infer gene flow depends on the sampling of populations (Petit *et al.*, 2005; Besnard *et al.*, 2021). Although the R estimate can help comparing the relative contribution of pollen and seeds in global gene flow among taxa (Ennos, 1994; Petit *et al.*, 2005), it thus still needs to be interpreted with caution.

RESULTS

All loci were successfully amplified in all *Chrysojasminum fruticans* individuals freshly collected in southern France and Spain (whole dataset provided in the Supporting Information, Table S1), and all revealed polymorphisms. A few genets with several ramets were identified in populations 'La Aliseda', 'Amélie-les-Bains', 'Prades-le-Lez', and 'La Turbie'. These genets can cover a relatively large surface (up to about 90 m² for an individual of the Spanish population 'La Aliseda'). Only one ramet per genet was subsequently kept for our analyses (for a total of 186 genets). Among the 179 genets sampled in France, 89 were recorded as brevistylous and 90 as longistylous (Table 1). In addition, most of our markers yielded amplifications with herbarium samples, pointing out their high potential to analyze genetic variation in old specimens collected more than 100 years ago. Cytoplasmic markers revealed the presence of seven chlorotypes and six mitotypes in French populations, most of them being shared with the few analyzed individuals from the Southern Iberian Peninsula to the Eastern Maghreb (e.g. all mitotypes, and chlorotypes 1, 3, 4 and 7; Supporting Information, Table S1). By combining cpDNA and mtDNA information, 20 cytoplasmic haplotypes were identified in southern France (Table 2), where five of the six mitotypes were associated with more than one chlorotype, and five of the seven chlorotypes were associated with more than one mitotype. Consequently, the LD between haplotypes of the two organellar genomes, measured according to Lewontin (1964), was relatively low ($D' = 0.368$, p -value < 0.001) compared to other plants where such data are available [e.g. $D' > 0.95$ in *Olea europaea* (Besnard *et al.*, 2002), *Silene vulgaris* (Olson & McCauley, 2000), and *Beta vulgaris* (Desplanque *et al.*, 2000)]. However, relatively strong and significant LD between organellar genomes was found at the population scale (*i.e.* 'La Aliseda' and 'CEFE'; $D' > 0.88$, p -value < 0.005 ; Supporting Information, Table S7). Overall, a non-strict association between haplotypes of both cytoplasmic genomes indicates that organelles are not always inherited together (implying paternal leaks). Yet, analyses of all 36 progenies only revealed a maternal inheritance of the two organellar genomes (Supporting Information, Table S6), suggesting that paternal leaks may be occasional. Consequently, the structure of organellar DNA diversity should be mostly influenced by seed dispersal. In addition, all 36 crosses involved a pair of brevistylous and longistylous individuals (24 B x L and 12 L x B; Supporting Information, Table S6).

STRUCTURE OF THE NUCLEAR GENETIC DIVERSITY ON THE WHOLE SAMPLE

The genetic proximity between all individuals of *C. fruticans* is represented by a dendrogram (Supporting Information, Fig. S1). All individuals from French populations were clustered together. Individuals from the same population were generally found in the same group suggesting a strong structure of populations in the South of France. Individuals from the Spanish population 'La Aliseda' formed the closest cluster to the French populations. Individuals from the rest of the Mediterranean were more distant from French and Spanish populations, except for individuals from Tunisia and Portugal.

This analysis also showed that individuals from Iran and Turkmenistan are very similar to each other and genetically the most distant from all other individuals analyzed.

Table 2. Association between mitotypes and chlorotypes on all *C. fruticans* individuals collected in southern France (179 individuals). Occurrence number of each chlorotype-mitotype combination is reported. Based on these data, the LD between haplotypes of the two organellar genomes, measured according to Lewontin (1964), was relatively low, but still highly significant ($D' = 0.368$, p -value < 0.001).

Mitotype no	Chlorotype no							Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1	36		26	3	1	8		74
2	6		1	3				10
3	2		4	3			1	10
4	37	12	10	15			2	76
5				1				1
6				5		3		8
Total	81	12	41	30	1	11	3	179

Table 3. Summary of genetic diversity parameters estimated within populations with at least seven individuals. Expected and observed heterozygosities were calculated using GENETIX (Belkhir *et al.*, 2004), the allelic richness (A_R) with the R package HIERFSTAT (Goudet, 2005), and the haplotypic diversities (D) according to Gryta *et al.* (2017). Parameters estimated per locus are given in the Supporting Information (Table S8). A_R = Allelic richness, H_E = Expected heterozygosity under Hardy-Weinberg, H_O = Observed heterozygosity, D_{cp} = Chloroplast haplotype diversity, D_{mt} = Mitochondrial haplotype diversity, D_{cp+mt} = Cytoplasmic haplotype diversity.

Population	Nuclear DNA			Cytoplasmic DNA		
	A_R	H_E	H_O	D_{cp}	D_{mt}	D_{cp+mt}
La Aliseda	3.17	0.42	0.45	0.76	0.76	0.76
Bages	3.38	0.50	0.49	0.53	0.44	0.65
Celleneuve	3.32	0.47	0.47	0.10	0.10	0.19
CEFE	3.78	0.55	0.57	0.70	0.53	0.70
Prades-le-Lez	3.21	0.47	0.51	0.69	0.00	0.69
St-Maurice-de-Navacelles	3.89	0.56	0.58	0.63	0.76	0.91
Moussoulens	3.32	0.50	0.54	0.75	0.75	0.83
Puycelsi	3.36	0.50	0.46	0.44	0.54	0.74
Bidon	3.29	0.49	0.58	0.36	0.00	0.36
Sainte-Baume	2.84	0.41	0.46	0.20	0.20	0.20
Eguilles	3.19	0.47	0.52	0.38	0.20	0.38
Moulis	2.36	0.35	0.37	0.11	0.47	0.50

GENETIC DIVERSITY OF POPULATIONS ANALYSES

Most nuclear loci revealed polymorphism within populations, even the di-allelic indel markers (Supporting Information, Table S8). Nevertheless, a few loci were not variable in some populations, especially in 'Moulis' (eight loci) and 'La Aliseda' (six loci). Among populations, most loci showed no excess of homozygosity or significant deviation from expected heterozygosities at the Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium, suggesting that the species reproduces mainly via outcrossing. For all populations, the global F_{IS} value was thus not significantly different from 0. The MICRO-CHECKER analysis detected probable presence of null allele in only five populations for one locus each (Cf-TA-1 for 'Bages', Cf-

ATT2 for 'CEFE', Cf-GAA19 for 'Moulis', Cf-GAA22 for 'St-Maurice-Navacelles', and Cf-GAA4 for 'Puycelsi', with respectively the followings Brookfield estimates of null allele frequencies: 0.019, 0.215, 0.093, 0.079, and 0.154). Considering the multiple tests performed (*i.e.* 29 loci x 12 populations), such observations may be fortuitous and all loci should have a very low frequency of null alleles. Finally, the average expected heterozygosity and allelic richness (calculated for seven diploid individuals) showed that 'Moulis' ($H_E = 0.35$; $A_R = 2.36$) is genetically impoverished compared to all other populations ($0.41 < H_E < 0.56$; $2.84 < A_R < 3.89$; Table 3). The highest level of nuclear diversity was revealed in 'St-Maurice-Navacelles'.

Most populations showed polymorphisms on both chloroplast and mitochondrial genomes (Fig. 2; Supporting Information, Table S8), with a maximum of five mitotypes in 'St-Maurice-Navacelles' and four chlorotypes in 'CEFE'. The combination of both genomes allowed us to detect from two to eight cytoplasmic haplotypes per population, with a haplotypic diversity (D_{cp+mt}) varying from 0.19 ('Celleneuve') to 0.91 ('St-Maurice-Navacelles'). Conversely to the nuclear genome, the 'Moulis' population did not show a particularly reduced diversity of cytoplasmic haplotypes ($D_{cp+mt} = 0.50$), although its chlorotype diversity was among the lowest ($D_{cp} = 0.11$; Table 2).

POPULATION STRUCTURE

The F_{ST} values calculated from the nuclear data supported a significant genetic differentiation between most pairs of populations (Supporting Information, Table S9). The dendrogram reconstructed from these F_{ST} (Supporting Information, Fig. S2) showed that geographically close populations were also genetically close, except in the case of 'Moulis', which was found here genetically more differentiated from the other French populations than the Spanish population was. Also, the artificial population of 'CEFE' (Montpellier) whose individuals originate from neighboring populations was found to be close to the other populations sampled near Montpellier ('Celleneuve' and 'Prades-le-Lez').

Figure 1. Results of the STRUCTURE analysis on ten French populations. A Bayesian approach was used to assign individuals to populations on the basis of their genotypes with STRUCTURE v.2.3.4 (Pritchard, Stephens & Donnelly, 2000). The analysis was performed for a number of clusters (K) ranging from 1 to 14 with ten iterations for each value of K . The most likely numbers of clusters were determined using the *ad hoc* measure of ΔK performed with STRUCTURE HARVESTER (Earl & vonHoldt, 2012). (A) Absolute values of the second-order rate of change of the likelihood distribution divided by the s.d. of the likelihoods (ΔK); (B) Mean log likelihood [$\ln(K)$ +/- s.d.] averaged over the ten iterations for each K value; (C) Barplots of the population structure for $K = 2$ and 10. Each genetic cluster is represented by a color. Each vertical bar corresponds to an individual with their percentage assignment (p) to the clusters. For $K = 2$, the population of 'Moulis' (in red) differs from the nine others (in green). At $K = 10$, the clusters correspond fairly well to the populations defined *a priori*.

An analysis performed with STRUCTURE on nuclear data from ten natural French populations (with at least ten genotypes) revealed the presence of several genetic clusters. Peaks in the graphical representation of ΔK (Fig. 1A) allowed the identification of population structuring at two levels: $K = 2$ and 10. For $K = 2$, 'Moulis' was distinguished from other populations (Fig. 1B), whereas the ten populations defined *a priori* were relatively well supported at $K = 10$ (Fig. 1C). The assignment of 'CEFE' individuals to these natural populations confirmed the putative origin of this artificial population from collects around Montpellier, since successful assignments (27% of genets) only concerned the three locations collected in Hérault ('St-Maurice-de-Navacelles', 'Celleneuve', and 'Prades-le-Lez'; Supporting Information, Table S10).

Genetic relationships between cytoplasmic haplotypes assessed by reduced-median network analyses (Fig. 2) showed three slightly differentiated lineages of chlorotypes (*i.e.* 1-2, 3-6, and 7) and no clear genetic structure for mitotypes. The geographical distribution of these chlorotypes and mitotypes (Fig. 2) did not show any clear pattern of geographical structuring. However, F_{ST} values calculated from these cytoplasmic data were relatively high and most of them were significantly different from 0 (Supporting Information, Table S8).

Figure 2. Distribution of (A) chloroplastic and (B) mitochondrial haplotypes in southwestern France. The haplotypes found in a Spanish population ('La Aliseda', Jaén Province) are also indicated. In the left-hand, top corner of each map, the reduced-median haplotype network (reconstructed with NETWORK v.10.2; Bandelt, Forster & Röhl, 1999) is given for each organellar genome.

ISOLATION BY DISTANCE AND CONTRIBUTION OF POLLEN AND SEEDS TO GLOBAL GENE FLOW

Strong IBD was observed for the nuclear data (Mantel test, $r = 0.528$, p -value = 0.004; Fig. 3A). In contrast, the cytoplasmic data did not show any isolation pattern by distance (Fig. 3B), regardless of how the F_{ST} values were calculated (*i.e.* based on cpDNA, mtDNA, or when combining information of both organellar genomes; Supporting Information, Fig. S3). Based on the estimates of global genetic differentiation between populations for nuclear markers ($F_{STn} = 0.17$, $F_{IS} = 0.17$) and cytoplasmic genomes ($F_{STc} = 0.50$), the Ennos's index ($R = 3.618$) showed that the contribution of the pollen to global gene flow is somewhat greater than that of seeds. However, this index was relatively low compared to many other plants (median $R = ca. 17$; Petit *et al.*, 2005).

Figure 3. Genetic differentiation between populations as a function of geographical distance for (A) nuclear and (B) cytoplasmic data. Tests of Mantel (1967) were done with 999 permutations using the R package *ade4* (Chessel, Dufour & Thioulouse, 2004). Genetic distances (F_{ST}) and geographical distances between population pairs show a significant relationship (Mantel test, $r = 0.528$, p -value = 0.003) for nuclear data, but not for cytoplasmic data ($r = -0.052$, p -value > 0.05).

DISCUSSION

This work represents the first population genetics study of *Chrysojasminum fruticans*. We mainly sampled populations in southern France and recorded floral morphs on all individuals. Genetic variation was then detected in the three genome compartments allowing revealing contrasting levels of diversity among populations as well as a strong genetic structure resulting from limited gene flow. It also brought information on the relative contribution of seeds and pollen in the global gene flow. Our results will have various methodological implications when developing genetic studies on this species, especially to study its reproductive and dispersal strategies.

First, our sampling in southern France revealed that both floral morphs have a balanced frequency among all populations (89 B vs. 90 L), and the few analyzed progenies (36) also confirmed that crosses should mainly occur between these two morphs (Dommée, Thompson & Cristini, 1992; Gutiérrez, Gutiérrez & Medrano, 1998). These preliminary observations are consistent with a diallelic self-incompatibility system but a wider sampling is still necessary, especially to measure how mating patterns vary among populations and floral morphs (for instance, to test if cross-compatibility or selfing rate vary among morphs in relation with stigma height or any other traits; Thompson & Dommée, 1993, 2000).

Then, a set of markers was developed for investigating variation of the three genomic compartments in *C. fruticans*. Such tools may have applications in different fields from population genetics and phylogeography to parentage analyses. Here, chloroplast and mitochondrial markers showed great potential for investigating the inheritance of both organellar genomes by either

investigating the linkage disequilibrium between chloroplast and mitochondrial haplotypes, or directly by checking their inheritance in progenies. The low linkage disequilibrium on the whole sample supports a non-strict maternal inheritance in *C. fruticans* as already documented in other Jasmineae (Sodmergen *et al.*, 1998; Zhang, Liu & Sodmergen, 2003), but our preliminary progeny analyses indicate that paternal leakage should be rare. Consequently, we used organellar DNA polymorphism for investigating seed dispersal. Furthermore, nuclear microsatellite markers may be useful in assisting the identification of genets in populations and in determining fine population structure to further study demographic processes at a local scale. Here, they revealed shared genotypes by close ramets indicating the presence of clones in the investigated populations due to vegetative growth. The shoots of a single stump can cover up to several tens of m² (as already observed in olive trees; Baali-Cherif & Besnard, 2005), indicating *a priori* a long persistence of certain individuals. Based on our observations, avoiding multiple sampling of the same genotype in population genetic studies may therefore require collecting ramets at least ten meters apart.

Once the clones were removed, our population analysis showed a strong structure of the genetic diversity in *C. fruticans* (*i.e.* high differentiation between pairs of populations) on both nuclear and cytoplasmic data. In addition, strong IBD is observed on the nuclear data, but not on the cytoplasmic data (Fig. 3). The presence of a very strong IBD is common in insect-pollinated species with limited pollen and seed dispersal (e.g. Jump *et al.*, 2009). In *C. fruticans*, the pollen is sticky and should be mostly spread by various insects (Thompson, 2001) at the local scale. In contrast, fleshy fruits can be spread by birds (Puech, 1986), and the longest dispersal events may thus occur at a larger distance for seeds than for pollen, especially in a very fragmented landscape (e.g. García-Verdugo *et al.*, 2010; Trapnell *et al.*, 2022). The relative contribution of pollen and seeds to global gene flow reflects this expectation, with an *R* value inferior to 5 as frequently observed in most insect-pollinated and fleshy fruited species (Oddou-Muratorio *et al.*, 2001; Petit *et al.*, 2005). Furthermore, random long-distance dispersal by seeds through the landscape would lead to a patchy structure of organellar lineages in space (Petit *et al.*, 1997), and could explain the absence of IBD on both maternally inherited genomes. In addition, the plants mainly produced fruits in autumn (Puech, 1986) when migratory birds are travelling southwards, and a latitudinal pattern could thus be expected. It is noticeable that organellar haplotypes observed in southern France are shared with populations from the Southern Iberian Peninsula to the Eastern Maghreb, suggesting that seeds can indeed travel long distances with birds and could have even crossed the Mediterranean Sea, as already shown in another Mediterranean shrub, *Pistacia lentiscus* L. (Martinez-Lopez *et al.*, 2020). Nonetheless, it is possible that cytoplasmic haplotypes identified here have diverged a long time ago, and more variable loci would reveal some differentiation between such distant populations. It is thus presently too speculative to interpret our diversity patterns in the context of Mediterranean micro-refugia (*i.e.* south-eastern Pyrenees, southern Cevennes, Mont Ventoux, eastern Provence, Alpes Maritimes; Médail & Diadema, 2009), and a denser and wider sampling of the studied area would also be required for this purpose.

Finally, in a context of gene flow limitation, small marginal populations are expected to diverge rapidly. In our study, the 'Moulis' population is highly differentiated from the others and is genetically impoverished compared to other populations, supporting the fact that it is highly isolated. This population is relatively large (several hundred thousand individuals over several hundred ha), and its low diversity may be explained by a relatively recent expansion from a few founders. However, the necessity that recent populations were initially founded from at least two compatible individuals could be a constraint, and self-compatible individuals may be temporarily favored on the front of colonization to ensure reproduction (Baker, 1955; Pannell & Barrett, 1998). Although no significant inbreeding index was observed in all populations indicating that the species is mainly out-crossing, preliminary paternity analyses on seeds collected in 'Moulis' from two mother plants in two following years showed a high rate of self-fertilization (ca. 70%) on a brevistylous individual (unpublished data), suggesting that this population is indeed not completely allogamous as similarly reported in some populations of *Ligustrum vulgare* L. (de Cauwer *et al.*, 2021). Thus, effective selfing events could have also contributed to genetic diversity erosion of the 'Moulis' population.

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

Our results have several implications for further studies on the variation of mating strategies in *Chrysojasminum fruticans*. Variable levels of genetic diversity among unconnected populations imply contrasting demographic histories with possibly varying loads of deleterious mutations (e.g. Liu *et al.*, 2022). In a distylous species, if the selfing rate is higher in one morph than in the other, questions arise about the allocation of resources and their evolutionary consequences on the reproductive strategies (e.g. possible transition to cryptic dioecy). For this reason, it seems relevant to study mating of the common yellow jasmine in various contexts. One could first compare the rates of self-fertilization (by paternity analysis on seeds) on the two floral morphs in several populations, and in case of marked differences, study the associated inbreeding depression. If one morph is much more self-pollinating in some populations, it would also be very relevant to follow the investment of each morph in reproduction and vegetative growth (Dommée, Thompson & Cristini, 1992).

Finally, the artificial population on the experimental field of the 'CEFE' Montpellier (with approximately 200-300 mature individuals in a hedge of ca. 250 m²) may also offer some opportunities for studying mating in a semi-natural context. Our genetic data supported that individuals have mostly originated from different localities near Montpellier. Its high accessibility may allow long-term follow up of individuals (e.g. measure of their investment in sexual functions over years). Due to the limitation of gene flow by distance, this population can be considered as strongly isolated from natural stands (at several kilometers). It will be fully characterized with our markers in order to investigate pollen and seed dispersal, as well as mating between morphs (Besnard *et al.*, 2020). Microsatellite analyses should allow investigating pollen gene flow via paternity analyses of seeds, while recruitment over last decades could be investigated via reconstructing pedigrees (e.g. Bacles, Lowe & Ennos, 2006; Bittencourt & Sebben, 2007). Finally, cytoplasmic variation in the population could be useful to investigate the inheritance of organelles and estimate the rate of paternal leaks in known crosses.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

Genotype data generated in this study are provided in the Supporting Information (Table S1). Thirteen herbarium specimens were collected in Amélie-les-Bains, Bages, CEFE, Moulis, Moussoulens, and Puyelsi, and deposited at the Montpellier herbarium (MPU; HG-2023-001 to -005, and GB-2023-001 to -008).

REFERENCES

- Baali-Cherif D, Besnard G. 2005.** High genetic diversity and clonal growth in relict populations of *Olea europaea* subsp. *laperrinei* (Oleaceae) from Hoggar, Algeria. *Annals of Botany* **96**: 823–830.
- Bacles CFE, Lowe AJ, Ennos RA. 2006.** Effective seed dispersal across a fragmented landscape. *Science* **311**: 628–628.
- Baker HG. 1955.** Self-compatibility and establishment after "long-distance" dispersal. *Evolution* **9**: 347–348.
- Bandelt HJ, Forster P, Röhl A. 1999.** Median-joining networks for inferring intraspecific phylogenies. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* **16**: 37–48.
- Banfi E. 2014.** *Chrysojasminum*, a new genus for *Jasminum* sect. *Alternifolia* (Oleaceae, Jasmineae). *Natural History Sciences* **1**: 3–6.
- Barrett SCH. 2002.** The evolution of plant sexual diversity. *Nature Reviews Genetics* **3**: 274–284.
- Belkhir K, Borsa P, Chikhi L, Raufaste N, Bonhomme F. 2004.** GENETIX 4.05, logiciel sous Windows TM pour la génétique des populations. Laboratoire Génome, Populations, Interactions, CNRS UMR 5000, Université de Montpellier II, Montpellier (France).
- Besnard G, Cheptou PO, Debbaoui M, Lafont P, Huguely B, Dupin J, Baali-Cherif D. 2020.** Paternity tests support a diallelic self-incompatibility system in a wild olive (*Olea europaea* subsp. *laperrinei*, Oleaceae). *Ecology and Evolution* **10**: 1876–1888.

- Besnard G, Gorrilliot O, Raimondeau P, Génot B, El Bakkali A, Anthelme F, Baali-Cherif D. 2021. Contrasting genetic footprints among Saharan olive populations: potential causes and conservation implications. *Plants* **10**: 1207.
- Besnard G, Hernández P, Khadari B, Dorado G, Savolainen V. 2011. Genomic profiling of plastid DNA variation in the Mediterranean olive tree. *BMC Plant Biology* **11**: 80.
- Besnard G, Khadari B, Baradat P, Bervillé A. 2002. Combination of chloroplast and mitochondrial DNA polymorphisms to study cytoplasm genetic differentiation in the olive complex (*Olea europaea* L.). *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* **105**: 139–144.
- Billiard S, Husse L, Lepercq P, Godé C, Bourceaux A, Lepart J, Vernet P, Saumitou-Laprade P. 2015. Selfish male-determining element favors the transition from hermaphroditism to androdioecy. *Evolution* **69**: 683–693.
- Bittencourt JVM, Sebben AM. 2007. Patterns of pollen and seed dispersal in a small, fragmented population of the wind pollinated tree *Araucaria angustifolia* in southern Brazil. *Heredity* **99**: 580–591.
- Brookfield JFY. 1996. A simple new method for estimating null allele frequency from heterozygote deficiency. *Molecular Ecology* **5**: 453–455.
- Bruvo R, Michiels NK, D'Souza TG, Schulenburg H. 2004. A simple method for the calculation of microsatellite genotype distances irrespective of ploidy level. *Molecular Ecology* **13**: 2101–2106.
- Busch JW, Joly S, Schoen DJ. 2010. Does mate limitation in self-incompatible species promote the evolution of selfing? The case of *Leavenworthia alabamica*. *Evolution* **64**: 1657–1670.
- Charlesworth D. 2006. Evolution of plant breeding systems. *Current Biology* **16**: R726–R735.
- Chessel D, Dufour A, Thioulouse J. 2004. The ade4 package - I: One-table methods. *R News* **4**: 5–10.
- de Cauwer I, Vernet P, Billiard S, Godé C, Bourceaux A, Ponitzki C, Saumitou-Laprade P. 2021. Widespread coexistence of self-compatible and self-incompatible phenotypes in a diallelic self-incompatibility system in *Ligustrum vulgare* (Oleaceae). *Heredity* **127**: 384–392.
- Debussche M, Escarré J, Lepart J. 1982. Ornithochory and plant succession in Mediterranean abandoned orchards. *Vegetatio* **48**: 255–266.
- Desplanque B, Viard F, Bernard J, Forcioli D, Saumitou-Laprade P, Cuguen J, Van Dijk H. 2000. The linkage disequilibrium between chloroplast DNA and mitochondrial DNA haplotypes in *Beta vulgaris* ssp. *maritima* (L.): the usefulness of both genomes for population genetic studies. *Molecular Ecology* **9**: 141–154.
- Dommeé B, Thompson JD, Cristini F. 1992. Distylie chez *Jasminum fruticans* L.: Hypothèse de la pollinisation optimale basée sur les variations de l'écologie intraflorale. *Bulletin de la Société Botanique de France* **139**: 223–234.
- Dupin J, Raimondeau P, Hong-Wa C, Manzi S, Gaudeul M, Besnard G. 2020. Resolving the phylogeny of the olive family (Oleaceae): confronting information from organellar and nuclear genomes. *Genes* **11**: 1508.
- Earl DA, vonHoldt BM. 2012. STRUCTURE HARVESTER: A website and program for visualizing STRUCTURE output and implementing the Evanno method. *Conservation Genetics Resources* **4**: 359–361.
- Ennos RA. 1994. Estimating the relative rates of pollen and seed migration among plant-populations. *Heredity* **72**: 250–259.
- Excoffier L, Lischer HEL. 2010. ARLEQUIN suite ver 3.5: A new series of programs to perform population genetics analyses under Linux and Windows. *Molecular Ecology Resources* **10**: 564–567.
- García-Verdugo C, Forrest AD, Fay MF, Vargas P. 2010. The relevance of gene flow in metapopulation dynamics of an oceanic island endemic, *Olea europaea* subsp. *guanchica*. *Evolution* **64**: 3525–3536.
- Goudet J. 2005. HIERFSTAT, a package for R to compute and test hierarchical *F*-statistics. *Molecular Ecology Notes* **5**: 184–186.
- Gryta H, Van de Paer C, Manzi S, Holota H, Roy M, Besnard G. 2017. Genome skimming and plastid microsatellite profiling of alder trees (*Alnus* spp., Betulaceae): Phylogenetic and phylogeographical prospects. *Tree Genetics & Genomes* **13**: 118.
- Gutián J, Gutiérrez P, Medrano M. 1998. Floral biology of the distylous Mediterranean shrub *Jasminum fruticans* (Oleaceae). *Nordic Journal of Botany* **18**: 195–201.
- Jump AS, Rico L, Lloret F, Peñuelas J. 2009. Microspatial population genetic structure of the Mediterranean shrub *Fumana thymifolia*. *Plant Biology* **11**: 152–160.
- Kamvar ZN, Tabima JF, Grünwald NJ. 2014. Poppr: An R package for genetic analysis of populations with clonal, partially clonal, and/or sexual reproduction. *PeerJ* **2**: e281.
- Kearse M, Moir R, Wilson A, Stones-Havas S, Cheung M, Sturrock S, Buxton S, Cooper A, Markowitz S, Duran C, Thierer T, Ashton B, Meintjes P, Drummond A. 2012. GENEIOUS Basic: An integrated and extendable desktop software platform for the organization and analysis of sequence data. *Bioinformatics* **28**: 1647–1649.
- Lewontin RC. 1964. The interaction of selection and linkage. I. General considerations; heterotic models. *Genetics* **49**: 49–67.
- Lewontin RC. 1988. On measures of gametic disequilibrium. *Genetics* **120**: 849–852.
- Liu S, Zhang L, Sang Y, Lai Q, Zhang X, Jia C, Long Z, Wu J, Ma T, Mao K, Street NR, Ingvarsson PK, Liu J, Wang J. 2022. Demographic history and natural selection shape patterns of deleterious mutation load and barriers to introgression across *Populus* genome. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* **39**: msac008.
- Mantel N. 1967. The detection of disease clustering and a generalized regression approach. *Cancer Research* **27**: 209–220.
- Martínez-López V, García C, Zapata V, Robledano F, De la Rúa P. 2020. Intercontinental long-distance seed dispersal across the Mediterranean Basin explains population genetic structure of a bird-dispersed shrub. *Molecular Ecology* **29**: 1408–1420.
- Médail F, Diadema K. 2009. Glacial refugia influence plant diversity patterns in the Mediterranean Basin. *Journal of Biogeography* **36**: 1333–1345.
- Oddou-Muratorio S, Petit RJ, Le Guerroué B, Guesnet D, Demesure B. 2001. Pollen- versus seed-mediated gene flow in a scattered forest tree species. *Evolution* **55**: 1123–1135.
- Olesen JM, Dupont YL, Ehlers BK, Valido A, Hansen DM. 2003. Heterostyly in the Canarian endemic *Jasminum odoratissimum* (Oleaceae). *Nordic Journal of Botany* **23**: 537–539.
- Olson MS, McCauley DE. 2000. Linkage disequilibrium and phylogenetic congruence between chloroplast and mitochondrial haplotypes in *Silene vulgaris*. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series B* **267**: 1801–1808.
- Pannell JR, Barrett SCH. 1998. Baker's law revisited: reproductive assurance in a metapopulation. *Evolution* **52**: 657–668.
- Paetkau D, Slade R, Burden M, Estoup A. 2004. Genetic assignment methods for the direct, real-time estimation of migration rate: a simulation-based exploration of accuracy and power. *Molecular Ecology* **13**: 55–65.
- Petit RJ, Duminil J, Fineschi S, Hampe A, Salvini D, Vendramin GG. 2005. Comparative organization of chloroplast, mitochondrial and nuclear diversity in plant populations. *Molecular Ecology* **14**: 689–701.
- Petit RJ, Pineau E, Demesure B, Bacilieri R, Ducouso A, Kremer A. 1997. Chloroplast DNA footprints of postglacial recolonization by oaks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **94**: 9996–10001.
- Piry S, Alapetite A, Cornuet JM, Paetkau D, Baudouin L, Estoup A. 2004. GENECLASS2: A software for genetic assignment and first-generation migrant detection. *Journal of Heredity* **95**: 536–539.
- Pritchard JK, Stephens M, Donnelly P. 2000. Inference of population structure using multilocus genotype data. *Genetics* **155**: 945–959.
- Puech S. 1986. Production des diaspores et potentialités de germination chez quelques espèces à fruits charnus, ornithochores, dans le sud-est de la France. *Ecologia Mediterranea* **12**: 143–158.

- QGIS Development Team. 2018.** QGIS Geographic Information System. Open Source Geospatial Foundation Project. <https://qgis.org/>
- Rannala B, Mountain JL. 1997.** Detecting immigration by using multilocus genotypes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **94**: 9197–9201.
- Salmona J, Olofsson JK, Hong-Wa C, Razanatosoa J, Rakotonasolo F, Ralimanana H, Randriamboavonjy T, Suescun U, Vorontsova MS, Besnard G. 2020.** Late Miocene origin and recent population collapse of the savanna Malagasy olive (*Noronhia lowryi*). *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* **129**: 227–243.
- Saumitou-Laprade P, Vernet P, Vassiliadis C, Hoareau Y, de Magny G, Dommée B, Lepart J. 2010.** A self-incompatibility system explains high male frequencies in an androdioecious plant. *Science* **327**: 1648–1650.
- Schuelke M. 2000.** An economic method for the fluorescent labeling of PCR fragments. *Nature Biotechnology* **18**: 233–234.
- Slatkin M. 1987.** Gene flow and the geographic structure of natural populations. *Science* **236**: 787–792.
- Slatkin M. 1993.** Isolation by distance in equilibrium and non-equilibrium populations. *Evolution* **47**: 264–279.
- Sodmergen, Bai HH, He JX, Kuroiwa H, Kawano S, Kuroiwa T. 1998.** Potential for biparental cytoplasmic inheritance in *Jasminum officinale* and *Jasminum nudiflorum*. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **11**: 107–112.
- Sork VL. 2016.** Gene flow and natural selection shape spatial patterns of genes in tree populations: implications for evolutionary processes and applications. *Evolutionary Applications* **9**: 291–310.
- Thompson JD, Dommée B. 1993.** Sequential variation in the components of reproductive success in the distylous *Jasminum fruticans* (Oleaceae). *Oecologia* **94**: 480–487.
- Thompson JD, Dommée B. 2000.** Morph-specific patterns of variation in stigma height in natural populations of distylous *Jasminum fruticans*. *New Phytologist* **148**: 303–314.
- Thompson JD. 2001.** How do visitation patterns vary among pollinators in relation to floral display and floral design in a generalist pollination system? *Oecologia* **126**: 386–394.
- Trapnell DW, Smallwood PA, Dixon KW, Philipps RD. 2022.** Are small populations larger than they seem? Genetic insights into patchily distributed populations of *Drakaea glyptodon* (Orchidaceae). *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society* **198**: 99–116.
- Van Oosterhout C, Hutchinson W, Willis D, Shipley P. 2004.** MICRO-CHECKER: software for identifying and correcting genotyping errors in microsatellite data. *Molecular Ecology Notes* **4**: 535–538.
- Vassiliadis C, Valero M, Saumitou-Laprade P, Godelle B. 2000.** A model for the evolution of high frequencies of males in an androdioecious plant based on a cross-compatibility advantage of males. *Heredity* **85**: 413–422.
- Vernet P, Lepercq P, Billiard S, Bourceaux A, Lepart J, Dommée B, Saumitou-Laprade P. 2016.** Evidence for the long-term maintenance of a rare self-incompatibility system in Oleaceae. *New Phytologist* **210**: 1408–1417.
- Wallerander E, Albert VA. 2000.** Phylogeny and classification of Oleaceae based on *rps16* and *trnL-F* sequence data. *American Journal of Botany* **87**: 1827–1841.
- Weir BS, Cockerham CC. 1984.** Estimating *F*-statistics for the analysis of population structure. *Evolution* **38**: 1358–1370.
- Wolfe KH, Li WH, Sharp PM. 1987.** Rates of nucleotide substitution vary greatly among plant mitochondrial, chloroplast, and nuclear DNAs. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **84**: 9054–9058.
- Wright S. 1965.** The interpretation of population structure by *F*-statistics with special regard to systems of mating. *Evolution* **19**: 395–420.
- Zhang Q, Liu Y, Sodmergen. 2003.** Examination of the cytoplasmic DNA in male reproductive cells to determine the potential for cytoplasmic inheritance in 295 Angiosperm species. *Plant and Cell Physiology* **44**: 941–951.